

Table 2. Phenotypic correlations among plant type characters of the Aikawa 1/Chiyonishiki F₃ lines (n = 69).

Character ^a	Culm length (CL)	Panicle length (PL)	Panicles per plant (NP)	Total weight (TW)	Panicle weight (PW)	Harvest index (HI)	Single panicle weight (SPW)	Spikelets per panicle (NS)	Panicle density (PD)	Days to heading (NHD)
PL	0.442									
NP	-0.891	-0.446								
TW	-0.378	0.118	0.636							
PW	-0.348	0.256	0.567	0.960						
HI	0.089	0.500	-0.209	-0.081	0.194					
SPW	0.903	0.614	-0.914	-0.335	-0.248	0.308				
NS	0.869	0.624	-0.875	-0.341	-0.244	0.348	0.952			
PD	0.884	0.507	-0.887	-0.398	-0.316	0.291	0.939	0.990		
NHD	0.624	0.177	-0.452	-0.010	-0.046	-0.093	0.513	0.467	0.488	
PTI	0.858	0.467	-0.910	-0.503	-0.442	0.218	0.949	0.908	0.913	0.434

^a PTI (plant type index) = SPW/NP × 100. PD = NS/PL. Pr[|r| > 0.237] = 0.05, Pr[|r| > 0.3081] = 0.01, df = 67.

high-tillering and short-statured. F₁, F₂, and F₃ plants were transplanted. F₁ plants had intermediate plant type (Table 1). Mutant-type characters showed incomplete dominance in the F₁. Each character had a segregation ratio of 3 mutant:1 normal in the F₂. These mutant characters were completely associated in

the F₂ and F₃ plants. Thus F₂ segregated into 358:112 (mutant:normal), and gave a good fit to 3:1 ratio ($\chi^2 = 0.3433, 0.50 < P < 0.60$).

The F₃ lines derived from randomly sampled F₂ plants segregated into 23:31:15 (mutant:segregating:normal), and gave a good fit to a 1:2:1 ratio ($\chi^2 =$

2.913, 0.20 < P < 0.30). Several plant type characters, such as panicles per plant, spikelets per panicle, and culm length, showed either highly positive or negative correlations in the F₃ lines (Table 2). A single semidominant gene controls the low tillering trait, and this gene has pleiotropic effects on culm length and thickness, and panicle density.

Aikawa 1 and the true breeding F₃ lines of the mutant type had long culms that were very thick and sturdy and therefore resistant to lodging. These plants showed high seed fertility, erect leaf habit, and normal plant and grain development. The presence of these traits distinguishes this source of a major genic low tillering habit from others previously reported.

We are conducting yield trials under direct seeded conditions using several pairs of lines that are near isogenic except for the low tillering trait. □

Grain quality

Test of three rice grain quality characteristics

Zhang Xian-guang and Huang Yong-kai, Food Crops Research Institute, Hubei Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Wuhan 430064, China

We randomly chose 86 rice varieties of different origins from the International Rice Germplasm Center of IRRI and Hubei Province and used standard tests to determine amylose content (AC), gelatinization temperature (GT), and gel consistency (GC).

Distribution and performance of rice grain quality characteristics were country or region specific to some extent (see figure). In general, Japanese rice had low AC, low GT, and soft GC; most Korean rice had low AC and low to intermediate GT; IRRI (Philippine) varieties usually had high AC, low GT, and varying GC; Chinese varieties had varied characteristics across the four subgroups.

Samples from Japan, Korea, and central China had the most acceptable characteristics for japonica varieties: low to medium AC, low to intermediate GT,

Correlation coefficients among three quality characteristics by group.^a

Group or subgroup	Samples ^b (no.)	Examples	Correlation		
			AC—GT	AC—GC	GT—GC
IRRI	n ₁ = 22	IR8, IR20, IR36, IR54	-0.26	-0.45*	-0.15
	n ₂ = 23		-0.27	-0.39	-0.1
Japan	n ₁ = 10	Norin 9, Akage, Kuromochi	0	-0.61*	0
	n ₂ = 11		0	-0.59*	0
Korea	n ₁ = 9	Suk Na, Banto Kanon	0.53	-0.69*	-0.24
	n ₂ = 10		0.25	-0.80**	-0.02
China	n ₁ = 39		-0.68**	-0.85**	0.59**
	n ₂ = 42		-0.24	-0.85**	0.32*
Northern China	n ₁ = 10	Ta Ma Gu Chuan Nien	-0.97**	-0.92**	0.82**
Southern China	n ₁ = 9	Fu Lu Tsan, Chiu Erh Ai, Chen Ma Ai	-0.02	-0.10	-0.87**
	n ₂ = 10		0.79**	-0.83**	-0.95**
Central China	n ₁ = 11	Keng 73, E Yi 105, Yu Dao	0.24	-0.68*	-0.69*
	n ₂ = 13		0.78**	-0.87**	-0.78**
Taiwan	n = 9	Chianan 2, Liu Chow	-0.73*	-0.78*	0.64
Total	n ₁ = 80		-0.12	-0.53**	0.26*
	n ₂ = 86		-0.11	-0.59**	0.21

^a *,** = significant difference at 5% and 1% levels. ^b n₂ = n₁ + waxy varieties if present.

and soft to medium GC, the result of selecting to meet the preferences of consumers.

Some associations existed among the three characteristics though they differed with rice group and if waxy varieties

were included (see table). Waxy and very low AC varieties always had soft GC, clearly indicated by the significantly negative correlation. The relationships between AC and GT, and GT and GC were not as perfect as that between AC and GC. □

Frequency distribution of AC, GT, and GC of rice group or subgroup. a = IRRI, b = Japan, c = Korea, d₁ = northern China, d₂ = southern China, d₃ = central China, d₄ = Taiwan. Thirteen of the 86 varieties were in d₃ from Hubei, China. AC type: ▨ = waxy (2%), ▩ = very low (2-11.9%), ▧ = low (12-19.9%), ▦ = intermediate (20-24.9%), ▥ = high (≥25%); GT type: ▨ = low (alkali spreading values 6-7), ▩ = intermediate (4-5), ▧ = intermediate to high (3), ▦ = high (1-2); GC type: ▨ = soft (gel length 61-99 mm), ▩ = medium (41-60 mm), ▧ = medium to hard (36-40 mm), ▦ = hard (≤35 mm).

Grain quality of F₁ hybrids between wide-compatible japonica rice 02428 and indica varieties

Y. Shen, Q. Cai, and M. Gao, Institute of Nuclear-Agricultural Sciences (INAS), Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou 310029, China

We evaluated the grain quality of intersubspecies rice hybrids from the cross between six maternal indica varieties and wide-compatible paternal japonica rice 02428. Physicochemical characteristics were analyzed using standard methods.

The 1,000-grain weight of the six hybrids was 23.4-26.0 g, all within the range of their parents, except for Milyang

Physicochemical characters of indica-japonica rice hybrids at INAS, Hangzhou, China.

Variety or combination	1000-grain weight (g)	Hulling (%)	Length (mm)	L/W ratio	Chalkiness		Amylose content (%)	Gel consistency ^a (score 1-9)	Alkali digestion ^a (1-7)
					%	Score (0-9) ^a			
Shanyou 10 (check)	26.7	80.2	55	2.3	23.0	9	28.2	5	5
02428	24.2	79.7	44	1.6	50.0	9	18.5	5	3
IR1361	21.8	78.7	58	2.6	0.0	0	22.9	5	7
IR1361/02428	25.2	81.7	52	2.1	8.5	1	22.0	5	4
IR1362	22.3	80.6	51	2.1	0.5	0	21.9	9	7
IR1362/02428	23.4	81.6	51	2.0	5.5	1	17.2	1	4
IR1371	20.8	79.7	50	2.2	3.0	1	20.7	1	6
IR1371/02428	24.3	81.7	49	1.9	28.0	9	22.1	5	4
Milyang 46	25.6	80.4	54	2.3	2.0	1	21.3	9	6
Milyang 46/02428	26.0	82.4	51	2.0	11.5	5	16.9	9	5
Minghui 63	26.2	79.0	67	3.1	0.0	0	6.1	9	6
Minghui 63/02428	25.3	79.7	59	2.5	23.5	9	21.5	3	4
T64-7	22.5	78.5	67	3.5	12.5	5	28.4	9	3
T64-7/02428	23.5	81.1	57	2.3	5.0	1	28.3	1	3

^a Standard evaluation system for rice scale.